

Cover Letter

Dear Editor

Warm greetings!

I am glad to submit my manuscript entitled “The Effect of Urea Fertilization Rate and Harvesting Stage on Yield and Nutritive Value of Buffel Grass (*Cenchrus Ciliaris* Linn) Under Irrigation at Gewane District, Afar North Eastern Ethiopia for contemplation in journal of Environment Research Ecology. This study focuses on how to conserve both highly nutritious and yield of animal feed for animal producer through knowing the exact amount urea fertilizer and right stage of harvesting of forage using irrigation and finally to minimize the cost of animal feed, particularly for pastoral and agro-pastoral community in Afar, Ethiopia. To carry out the research land were select and prepared at Gewane College near Awash River. Throughout the research period plots were irrigated 7 day interval and weeding done according to the extent of the foreign plants and grass. The experiment was done for two season to see repeatability of the research. As the result season did not have any impact on the chemical composition and yield of the research grass. In general the result of the research showed that rate or level urea fertilizer application and stage of harvesting day had significance effect on the nutritive and yield of grass and can improve yield and quality of animal feed.

Thus, this manuscript plays for minimize cost animal feed, improve feed quality, and livelihood-oriented rangeland management, and policy maker to begin forage establishment and preservation using irrigation and finally it has its own contribution for ecological protection. This research paper is my original manuscript, unpublished and is not sent to any journal to publish.

Thank you for your valuable time and allowing my submission.

I would be happy and grateful to add value and work with to your journal.

Sincerely Yours,

Gebrehiwot Weleanania (MSc, in Animal Science, Raya University), PhD candidate at Mekelle University, Tigray, Ethiopia , Email: ghiwot2008@gmail.com

